

A novel open source tool for ELISA result analysis

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ABSTRACT

ELISA has become a standard analytical tool in the numerous branches of science and industry. Processing of the ELISA results may be a multistep process, often requiring a prior adaptation, using proprietary software, or exporting the results into external internet platforms. It may be problematic in the light of good documentation practices and maintaining good data integrity. In this paper, we present the development and application of the ELISA Tool software. The program is based on a Python scripting programming language and is available under an open-source license. The ELISA Tool allows users to fully control and validate the calculation procedure through a user-friendly graphical user interface. The modular architecture of the software allows its application in other information technology (IT) projects used for data processing in research laboratories. We successfully applied the ELISA Tool for the analysis of real-life samples. The ELISA Tool allowed import of the measurement data, an approximation of the calibration curves with two different algorithms, exploration and diagnostics of the model fit, and generation of the final report with the calculations while maintaining the raw data file unchanged. We report here for the first time the implementation of the idea of full control over data processing, from measured raw data to the final report. We obtained a transparent, open, registered system of data processing control, independent of third parties. The modular and flexible architecture of the created software encourages its further development following the individual demands of the users.

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1. Introduction

ELISA was invented in 1970s as a safer and more practicable technique than radioimmunoassay to measure the levels of clinically-relevant proteins in serum. Since that time, ELISA has undergone outstanding development, automation, and commercialization [1–3]. Owing to rapidness, relatively high selectivity, easy protocol, and relatively cheap equipment, the technique has become a common analytical tool in the numerous branches of science, industry, and services [1–6]. Currently, ELISA is an essential method in the analysis of proteins, peptides, antibodies, hormones, and vitamins for the purposes of medical diagnosis [1–3]. In clinical toxicology and forensic medicine, it enables fast qualitative screening and/or quantitative determination of different classes of drugs of abuse (e.g., amphetamines, opioids, and cannabinoids) and natural toxins (e.g., amanitin) in biological samples [4–7].

A new field for the application of ELISA in pharmaceutical analysis has been opened with ushering in the era of therapeutic

Abbreviations: 4PL, four-parameter logistic; 5PL, five-parameter logistic; AIC, Akaike Information Criterion; BCA, bicinchoninic acid; BIC, Bayesian Information Criterion; DE, DataExplore; GPL, general public license; IT, information technology; NDV, Newcastle disease virus; PDF, portable document format; RSS, Residual Sum of Squares; SOP, standard operating procedures; TMB, tetramethyl benzidine.

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monoclonal antibodies [7–10]. Over 100 of these biological agents are now licensed in the United States, and much more are under development worldwide [8,11]. They have dramatically improved the treatment of autoimmune diseases (e.g., rheumatoid arthritis, systemic lupus erythematosus), inflammatory bowel diseases (Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis), and some malignancies (e.g., breast, colorectal, and non-small lung cancers) [8–10]. Moreover, it has been reported that therapeutic drug monitoring of anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer monoclonal antibodies is clinically useful and cost-effective [9,10,12]. As ELISA is a method of choice for the quantification of therapeutic monoclonal antibodies, the importance of this technique in pharmaceutical analysis, including quality control within GMP and clinical bioanalysis, will certainly rise with a further spread of biologics [7,9,10,12].

The concentration – response relationship in ELISA is inherently nonlinear, usually best fitted with a four- (4PL) or five-parameter logistic (5PL) model. Therefore, a finding of the optimal calibration curve equation and final results (analyte concentration in the sample) require the use of computer software performing iterative calculations [6,13,14]. In practice, the raw measurement data are processed in the program integrated with an ELISA plate reader or imported, in many cases after prior adaptation, into external software, including free internet platforms (e.g., MyAssays.com and elisaanalysis.com) [6,14]. The final results are reported in an appropriate system according to the laboratory standard operating procedures (SOP). Every step of data processing is associated with many threats to the consistency and reliability of the output results, for example writing the data in closed format files, ignorance of data processing procedures by the software used, lack of logging of activities performed during the handling of programs, or the user's errors [15]. The problem of 'data integrity' in GMP and other GXP's (Good Clinical/Distribution/Laboratory/Pharmacovigilance Practice) is now intensively raised by the FDA, European Medicines Agency, and Medicines & Healthcare products Regulatory Agency, which undertake efforts to improve controlling of this issue [16–18]. As the ELISA analysis results may often condition making critical decisions, e.g., in medical diagnosis, drug dose optimization, forensic expertise on the use of illicit substances, medicinal product batch release, or marketing authorization of a new drug, the integrity of the ELISA data needs careful maintenance and control [1–11,15–20].

In this paper, we have developed the first open software for fully controlled and transparent processing of the ELISA measurements from their generation to reporting the final results. The modular structure of the solution will allow its easy implementation in a web services form under Laboratory Information Management System or Electronic Laboratory Notebook.

To develop an IT tool supporting work with ELISA, adapted to our current and future needs, we selected the Python [21] environment with the specialized libraries: NumPy [22], SciPy [23], Matplotlib [24], and Pandas [25]. The ELISA Tool (ET) presented at this work has been implemented as an extension of another opensource tool, DataExplore (DE) [26], a data analysis program. In order to obtain the highest possible quality of the created solution, we decided to publish the code under the open general public license (GPL), so that all interested and potential users would be able to independently assess the quality of the tool or participate in its development.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

A Newcastle disease virus (NDV) antibody ELISA-based test kit, containing NDV-coated plates, conjugate solution, sample dilu-

ent, tetramethyl benzidine (TMB) substrate, and stop solution, was obtained from IDEXX Laboratories, Inc. (Westbrook, ME, USA). Pierce™ bicinchonimic acid (BCA) protein assay kit was obtained from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA). For all dilutions and aqueous solutions an ultrapure water from a UV filtering system was used (GenePure Pro, Thermo Scientific Barnstead). Other reagents used in the experiment, including salts and organic solvents, were of analytical grade.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Basic ELISA

NDV was determined in egg yolk with the commercially available ELISA test. Since the obtained test was devised to detect NDV in chicken serum, it was necessary to perform an additional validation in terms of linearity, pipetting effect, inter- and intraplate variability, incubation times, replacement of PBS with NDV-negative yolk extract, freeze-thaw stability, and influence of different ion species.

2.2.1.1. Internal standard (IS) and sample preparation. In the first step, an IS was prepared from commercially available egg yolk from deep litter indoor housing chicken, which were NDV-immunized. Ten gram of spray-dried egg yolk was incubated at 37 °C for 20 min in 140 mL of PBS. Then, 40 mL of chloroform was added to remove lipids and the mixture was further incubated for 15 min at the same temperature. The aqueous phase was separated after centrifugation at 1850 × g for 20 min, lyophilized, and grinded. Obtained IS powder contained extracted proteins and salts. One gram of the IS dissolved in water resulted in a 9.3 mg/mL protein solution, as determined by the BCA protein assay.

2.2.1.2. Analysis protocol. Before measurement, the samples containing 25 mg of the lyophilized IS per 1 mL of PBS were serially diluted with PBS to achieve the appropriate nominal relative protein concentrations. Since a different matrix was used in the analysis (egg yolk instead of serum), the test validation procedure used a data-rich calibration curve, with protein concentrations [μg/mL] as follows: 10,000, 5000, 4000, 3000, 2000, 1000, 500, 450, 400, 350, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 50, 40, 30, 25, 20, 15, 12.5, 10, 7.5, 5, 2.5, 2, 1.5, 1, and 0.5. Once the validation confirmed the robustness of the ELISA test, a six point calibration curve was further used to determine NDV antibody in the studied egg yolk samples, with protein concentrations as follows: 2000, 500, 200, 80, 40, and 20 μg/mL.

The prepared standards or test samples were diluted two-fold with a sample diluent buffer provided by the ELISA kit manufacturer. The procedure was performed as advised by the manufacturer. Briefly, the 100 μL aliquots of samples were dispensed into a preheated ELISA plate, and incubated for 30 min at 18–26 °C. Unbound protein was washed out with distilled water. Once the conjugate solution was dispensed, the plates were further incubated for 30 min, and then washed repeatedly with distilled water. Finally, the TMB substrate was added into each well. After a 15 min incubation, the stop solution was added. Then, the plate was transferred to a Tecan Infinite 200 plate reader (Tecan Group Ltd., Männedorf, Switzerland) and the absorbance measurement was performed at 650 nm. Data acquisition and analysis were performed with an i-control™ ver. 1.11 software.

2.2.2. Raw data and input data

ELISA Tool was tested on the files imported from the TECAN Infinite® microplate reader. This line of devices is controlled by the i-control™ program and the manufacturer recommends a separate Magellan™ program to analyze results. TECAN Infinite® microplate reader records data in Microsoft Excel files, both xls and xlsx. The developed ELISA Tool reads these file formats using Python Pandas

Fig. 1. Interface of DataExplore and active plugin ELISA Tool.

library functions. The examples of the resultant xls/xlsx files are included as Supplementary Online files. In order to guarantee the integrity of saved measurement results, the ELISA Tool treats the file as read-only. All information necessary for further processing of the raw data is collected in an additional xls/xlsx file, called the *mapping file*. Together with the measurement file and calculation report makes a complete documentation of the experiment. The data import ends with a parsing procedure, which validates the mapping of raw data and file structure, and calculates mean values and deviations resulting from the measurement itself.

2.2.3. Calculation methods

To guarantee transparent data processing in ELISA Tool, well-tested numerical functions from Python libraries SciPy – *curve_fit* (cf) [23] and *differential_e_volution* (de)- were used for the interpolation of the absorbance results. The first technique uses non-linear least squares to fit an interpolation model to the experimental data, and a second one finds the global minimum of a multivariate function [23,27]. The both methods used are based on different approaches, but they give similar results in a wide range of applications. However, in many difficult cases, they require different amounts of computing power and can lead to different results. Stochastic methods used in *differential_e_volution* allow searching of large areas of possible solutions for more difficult cases. ELISA Tool is intended to provide a common interface for various existing and developing mathematical methods for data analysis in an ELISA experiments, allowing the user to make an informed choice of the best solution for his problem with full control over the calculation method.

2.2.4. Installation

The ELISA Tool installation takes place in two steps. Firstly, downloading and installation of the DataExplore program (DE)

from <https://dmnfarrell.github.io/pandastable/> [26] is carried out. Then the ELISA Tool plugin is downloaded in the form of a zip archive from [28], unpacked and copied to the DE plugin directory. After running DE, selection of *Install Plugin* and then *elisa tool plug.py* from the *Plugins Menu* installs and displays ELISA Tool in *Plugins Menu*. The installed program is ready for operation after restarting the DE. Once the ELISA Tool is selected from the list of plugins, its interface is displayed in the lower left corner of the DE window as presented in Fig. 1.

2.2.5. Interface and operation

The interface of the ELISA Tool plugin is organized in the form of three tabs: *Approximation*, *Configuration* and *Validation*. In the *Approximation* tab calculations are made on the raw data, and the *Validation* tab is used to validate the calculation procedure. Both of the tabs are structured in two columns, *Method* and *Commands* (Fig. 1). Due to the dispersion of data values that can occur in the experiment, calculations can be performed on appropriate systems: from *lin_lin* (input data are not modified), through *ln_lin* and *lin_lin* (corresponding data in logarithmic form) to *ln_lin* (all input data in logarithmic form). The choice of data system is made from the *Configuration* tab from the *Input Form* list.

In a first step of the ELISA Tool operation, one of the curve fitting methods – logarithmic (LN), 4-parameter logistic (4PL), 5-parameter logistic (5PL) or linear (LIN) – is selected from the drop down list in the *Method* column, in the *Approximation* tab. The *curve_fit* and *diff_e_vol* extensions in the method names refer to the functions used in their implementation from the SciPy, *curve_fit* or *differential_e_volution* library. The values of the lower and upper limits of the calibration curve model parameters (A to E, if applicable) are displayed below in the same column. A user can change the default limits accordingly to the case being examined. It is worth noting that *differential_e_volution* method is more efficient and

accurate than *curve_fit* in searching for the optimal solutions when the limits range is wide. The *curve_fit* works much faster computationally, but may fail in more difficult calculations. The employed optimization algorithms are controlled in two ways: by introducing initial estimated values of optimization parameters that are close to the final values, or by introducing a wide range of values for each parameter. In the ELISA Tool, we implemented the second solution. The user may choose to enter a narrower range of expected parameter values when additional information on expected values is known, for example from preliminary experiments. The user may also choose to explore comprehensively a wider range of parameter values for possible solutions when necessary. Of note, when ELISA Tool reports a parameter value equal to one of the designated ranges, it suggests that the solution is suboptimal and the algorithms are unable to minimize the fitting function within provided parameter ranges. In that case, the user should adjust the range limits by expanding them or shifting to include the expected value.

A next operation step, taking place in the *Commands* column, is the selection of the xls or xlsx file with the measurement results (*Read raw data* button) and the mapping file containing information about the experiment configuration (*Setup* button). The selected files are immediately read by the ELISA Tool and displayed in the upper window. It is worth mentioning that any change in the content of the raw data made in the DE sheet will not be considered in the calculations. Subsequently, a verification of the consistency of the input data is performed with the *Check* button. If the compatibility test passes without errors, the location and name for the final report file can be set up, standard points are displayed in the DE sheet and figure, and calculations can be started (*Calculate* button). The calculations are in progress when the displayed status is *Started*, and finished when the *Completed* status appears. The report document is saved as a portable document format (PDF) file. Moreover, the results of the best-fitted curve as well as test samples concentrations are displayed in the DE sheet in a numerical form. Also, the calibration curve is plotted in a graphics window. These data can be further processed with the DE tools and saved as a DE project.

ELISA Tool provides a variety of parameters to assess the quality of the calibration curve model fitting to the calibration standards measurement results: the Residual Sum of Squares (RSS), Coefficient of Determination (R^2), Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), Coefficient of Correlation (r). The model selection criteria and the goodness-of-fit related parameters are listed in the PDF file report.

2.2.6. Validation of the approximation methods

In the validation procedure, ELISA Tool examines the influence of noise on the quality of the estimates obtained from the selected approximation model. The validation relies on the generation of n_i points of the selected approximation function and addition of a random noise, of which level is controlled by the *noise* coefficient. To setup the validation procedure, the approximation function with the *val* extension is first indicated in the *Method* column. Subsequently, the noise figure, which defines the level of blurring of the test function in the interval $[0, 1]$, and the number of points describing the function are selected. The latter parameter usually ranges from 6 to 40, whereas the reasonable range of noise used for the input data is between 0 and 0.02. The setting of noise = 0 allows to obtain the start values of the parameters at which the input data were generated. The ranges of both the parameters for each validated approximation function are set permanently in the program. The result of the validation is saved in the reports directory as a figure file, text log file, and also csv file including numerical data.

The selection of an appropriate curve fitting model to describe the analyzed data requires a user's own experience and should not be automated. Conducting of validation tests allows the user to become familiar with the relationship between the quality of

Fig. 2. Approximation of the 4PL curve of the measurement results in the ELISA Tool using the differential_evolution function.

the analyzed data and the results that can be expected from the individual regression methods.

2.2.7. Mapping and report file

To describe the absorption measurements from a 96-wells plate, the language of simple commands is used: *stdNo* – standard No, *samNo* – sample No, *zero* – reference sample, etc. Calculations of means values and standard deviations are performed automatically for each well group with identical markings. Unmarked wells are not included in the calculations. This ELISA Tool's language can be further developed to support specific applications of the ELISA method. The mapping file acts as the log file of the experiment. It contains the information on the measurement and also the data included in the raw data file which are necessary for the results interpretation. Additional tables in the Mapping file records relevant information about the experiment conditions. The *key : value* notation is used to allow positioning the output data in appropriate places in the final report. The report is a PDF document containing all the data and information requested by the laboratory's SOP. The mapping and report files together with the raw data file form the SOP documentation, which can be digitally signed and distributed as intended. The sample mapping and report files are available as Online Supplementary Files.

3. Results

The final report document generated in ELISA Tool contains: results of the absorbance measurement for the calibration standards, selected approximation (curve fitting) model, absorbance results for the tested samples, respective concentrations in the tested samples calculated from the calibration curve, and corresponding graphs with a linear and linear-logarithmic scale. The examples of graphs obtained for the same measurement results with 4PL and 5PL methods are presented in Figs. 2 and 3, respectively.

ELISA Tool was used to compare the LN, 4PL, 5PL and LIN approximations for the measurement results of the calibration standards of NDV antibody in egg yolk. LN function gave the same values of the model estimates values ($A = 0.21599$, $B = 0$) and also fitting quality parameters (R^2 , RSS, and AIC) for both the *fc* and *de* algorithms, however the *fc* algorithm was more than 40 times faster (Table 1, Time column). When applying the 4PL model, the differences in the curve estimates and fitting parameters obtained with *fc* and *de* were very small ($D_{fc} = 1.4058$, $A_{fc} = 0.27174$, $B_{fc} = 1.3951$, $C_{fc} = 59.986$, $D_{de} = 1.4056_{de}$, $A_{de} = 0.27259$, $B_{de} = 1.3967$, $C_{de} = 60.050$). Using the 5PL model, *fc* and *de* algorithms also

Fig. 3. Approximation of the 5PL curve of the measurement results in the ELISA Tool using the differential evolution function.

Table 1

Comparison of the efficiency of implementation of computational algorithms *fit_curve* and *differential.equation*.

Methods	R^2	RSS	AIC	Time (s)
LN_{fc}	0.90108	8.61e-03	-19.78	0.0154
LN_{de}	0.90108	8.61e-03	-19.78	0.6779
$4PL_{fc}$	0.99996	3.34e-06	-55.050	0.0282
$4PL_{de}$	0.99996	3.34e-06	-55.046	7.9043
$5PL_{fc}$	1.0	0.0	-249.185	0.0804
$5PL_{de}$	1.0	0.0	-352.590	199.394

produced negligible differences in the model parameter values ($D = 1.4474$, $A = 0.37111$, $B = 2.002$, $C = 39.806$, $E = 0.48221$). Overall, the time of *de* calculations greatly increased with the increasing number of fitting parameters, in opposition to *fc*. In particular, *fc* was approximately 300 and 2000 faster than *de* for the 4PL and 5PL model, respectively (Table 1). Nevertheless, it is worth mentioning that the *fc* algorithm fails completely in more difficult analyses of measurement data, whereas the *de* algorithm returns good quality results. The values of R^2 , RSS, and AIC clearly indicated the 5PL model as the best fitted in the studied case.

4. Discussion

In the paper, we describe a novel tool for a comprehensive analysis of ELISA assay, written in the Python programming language, and using acknowledged open source libraries, such as *SciPy* or *NumPy*. The tool implements two different approximation algorithms for most commonly used curve fitting methods. Another feature of the tool is the possibility of assessment of the influence of noise on the quality of results obtained with a selected approximation model. We also demonstrate the application and efficacy of the tool in the analysis of the NDV assay results. We obtained an optimal curve fit for a standard six point curve, and a data point-rich curve. Fast and dynamic development in the field of computer science has led to the popularization of open solutions, modular architectures, technologically independent as well as low maintenance and development costs. Free and open source programming languages, such as Python or R, are widely used by researchers and data scientists. For this reason, we decided to develop the ELISA Tool in the Python language, as an extension of a DE program [26]. We provided a user-friendly graphical interface that allows an easy access to the fitting algorithms. ELISA Tool employs three regression methods – 4PL, 5PL, and a logarithmic regression. The user may also choose between two interpolation techniques – a non-linear least squares *curve_fit* or a stochastic-based *differen-*

Fig. 4. Comparison of differential evolution approximation results for six points of standard (red point with error bars) for two functions: LN (black solid line) and 5PL (blue dashed line). The absolute difference of 4PL and 5PL curves (green dashed line) refers to the right vertical axis. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

tial evolution. Currently, the regulatory agencies advise use of a minimum of six calibration standards and fit the curve with a non-linear regression model, preferably 4PL or 5PL [29]. Usually, the 5PL model is a good default model for a nonlinear calibration [30]. However, the numerical problems during fitting the 5PL model can lead to erroneous results of parameter estimates [31]. When comparing approximation results from different methods, as in Fig. 4, the appropriate method should be selected not only due to the level of compliance with standard deviations of approximated points, but also the asymptotic behavior of the method should be considered. Visually and statistically, a better fit of the 4PL and 5PL curves than the LN curve does not have to lead to better results when the methods are extrapolated beyond the range of measured standards. The difference (4PL-5PL), shown in Fig. 4, is an important clue as to the level of error introduced into data analysis by choosing from slightly different methods. The ultimate choice of a model depends on the knowledge and experience of the user. The ELISA Tool supports the user's choice with a number of goodness-of-fit diagnostic parameters (RSS, R^2 , AIC, BIC, and r). Additionally, DE program instantaneously displays obtained regression curve, standards, and sample measurements. This allows the user an effortless visual examination of the fit. Finally, the report file generated by the ELISA Tool supplies the user with the data needed for adequate reporting of valid assay results, such as bias, number of calibrator that meet the acceptance criteria, R^2 criterion, as well as raw and back-calculated data.

The data used in the paper are the results of NDV assay, but the ELISA Tool can effectively fit any data to the implemented non-linear models based on logistic regression. 4PL and 5PL fits are most widely used in immunoassays, which include not only ELISA, but also RIA, LIA. As mentioned previously, these methods are commonly used for diagnostic purposes to determine numerous types of chemical entities, including hormones (e.g., thyroid-stimulating hormone), cardiac markers, or antibodies to viruses [1,2]. Immunoassays are also used for the therapeutic monitoring of monoclonal antibodies [36]. Therefore, the ELISA Tool can find application in the field of biomedical and pharmaceutical analysis. The asset of the ELISA Tool is the ability to use it as an in-house solution. The results would be obtained without the need to employ an external proprietary software or internet-based services that could compromise the data anonymity or without the risk of security breach. The latter is especially important in the development of novel drugs.

One of the main advantages of the ELISA Tool is an automatically generated, detailed analysis report. The format of the report is a non-editable PDF document. This type of a data file is in accor-

dance with a general notion of data integrity. The latest consensus of the scientific community states that data integrity should rely upon quality and being honest, and that researchers should ensure completeness, accuracy, and consistency of data [15]. Within its life cycle, data undergoes multiple steps, from collection, through processing, reporting, and reviewing, to archiving. At each point a question arises – what documentation should be stored with the study file that can help with maintaining integrity of the data, and what risk of data manipulation exists. Most widely acknowledged protocol for good documentation practices is an ALCOA protocol [32]. ALCOA is the acronym that describes key attributes for good documentation: attributable, legible, contemporaneous, original and accurate. The latest guidelines encourage using an ALCOA Plus, which expands to Enduring, Available and Accessible, Complete, Consistent, Credible, and Corroborated [33]. Ideally, the archived study data and protocol should answer the basic questions, such as who generated the data, what the raw data results are, when the data was processed, why the data were transformed or altered, and where the data and report were generated. The ELISA Tool report stores all of these information. Moreover, all of the data imported into the ELISA Tool are treated as read-only, which minimizes the risk of possible parsing and sorting errors in the input Excel file, which can be the source of multiple downstream errors [34]. The proposed system in the ELISA Tool is the most convenient solution. The more advanced solution for ensuring maintenance of the data integrity, as well as proper documentation of all manipulations performed, would be a system based on blockchain mechanisms, such as Ethereum [35].

5. Conclusion

A method for a fully controlled, complete flow of electronic data from ELISA-based measurement to the final report of calculations is presented. The method is based on: file with measurement data – with unchangeable content, mapping file – log file with description of the experiment configuration edited by the user, calculation report – non-editable PDF file containing calculation results, ELISA.Tool – script performing calculation and formatting report according to the requirements of laboratory SOP. In this way, a transparent, open, registered system of data processing control is obtained, independent of third parties. Automation of measurement data processing using a widely available scripting programming language is the basis for recording the process of a scientific experiment. The modular and flexible architecture of the created software assumes its further development in accordance with individual demands of the users.

6. Author statement

Dorota Danielak: Writing – Original Draft, Review & Editing, Validation, Methodology; **Grzegorz Banach:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing – Original Draft, Review & Editing; **Juliusz Walaszczyk:** Software; **Michał Romanski:** Writing – Original Draft, Review & Editing; **Marek Bawiec:** Methodology, Software; **Jadwiga Paszkowska:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation; **Monika Zielinska:** Visualization; **Jaroslav Sczodrok:** Investigation; **Marcela Wiater:** Writing, Validation, Investigation; **Dagmara Hoc:** Writing, Validation, Investigation; **Bartosz Kolodziej:** Software; **Grzegorz Garbacz:** Supervision, Funding acquisition

7. Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2020.113415>.

References

- [1] S. Aydin, A short history, principles, and types of ELISA, and our laboratory experience with peptide/protein analyses using ELISA, *Peptides* 72 (2015) 4–15.
- [2] R. Lequin, Enzyme immunoassay (EIA)/enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), *Clin. Chem.* 51 (2005) 2415–2418.
- [3] P. Tighe, R. Ryde, I. Todd, L. Fairclough, ELISA in the multiplex era: potentials and pitfalls, *Proteom. Clin. Appl.* 9 (2015) 406–422.
- [4] H.S.S. Schumacher, A novel immunoassay for quantitative drug abuse screening in serum, *J. Immunol. Methods* 436 (2018) 34–40.
- [5] C. Bever, B. Barnych, R. Hnasko, L.W. Cheng, L. Stanker, A new conjugation method used for the development of an immunoassay for the detection of amanitin, a deadly mushroom toxin, *Toxins* 28 (2018) 265.
- [6] S. Nummer, A. Weeden, C. Shaw, B. Snyder, T. Bridgeman, S. Qian, Updating the ELISA standard curve fitting process to reduce uncertainty in estimated microcystin concentrations, *MethodsX* 5 (2018) 304–311.
- [7] D. Pluim, W. Ros, M. van Bussel, D. Brandsma, J. Beijnen, J. Schellens, Enzyme linked immunosorbent assay for the quantification of nivolumab and pembrolizumab in human serum and cerebrospinal fluid, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.* 164 (2019) 128–134.
- [8] M. Ovacik, K. Lin, Tutorial on monoclonal antibody pharmacokinetics and its considerations in early development, *Clin. Transl. Sci.* 11 (2018) 540–552.
- [9] T.O. Munnink, M. Henstra, L. Segerink, K. Movig, P. Brummeluis-Visser, Therapeutic drug monitoring of monoclonal antibodies in inflammatory and malignant disease: translating TNF- α experience to oncology, *Clin. Pharmacol. Ther.* 99 (2016) 419–431.
- [10] K. Papamichael, A. Cheifetz, G. Melmed, P. Irving, N.V. Castele, P. Kozuch, L. Raffals, L. Baidoo, B. Bressler, S. Devlin, J. Jones, G. Kaplan, M. Sparrow, F. Velayos, T. Ullman, C. Siegel, Appropriate therapeutic drug monitoring of biologic agents for patients with inflammatory bowel diseases, *Clin. Gastroenterol. Hepatol.* 17 (2019) 1655–1668.
- [11] CDER List of Licensed Biological Products, Updated 8 October 2019, 2019 (accessed 18.10.19) <https://www.fda.gov/media/89589/download>.
- [12] V. Heron, W. Afif, Update on therapeutic drug monitoring in Crohn's disease, *Gastroenterol. Clin. North Am.* 46 (2017) 645–659.
- [13] Food and Drug Administration, Bioanalytical Method Validation. Guidance for Industry, 2018 (accessed 17.10.19) <https://www.fda.gov/files/drugs/published/Bioanalytical-Method-Validation-Guidance-for-Industry.pdf>.
- [14] R. Herman, P. Scherer, G. Shan, Evaluation of logistic and polynomial models for fitting sandwich-ELISA calibration curves, *J. Immunol. Methods* 339 (2008) 245–258.
- [15] C. Arfvidsson, D.V. Bedaf, M. Doig, S. Globig, M. Knutsson, M. Lewis, S. McDougall, M. Michi, N. Mokrzycki, P. Timmerman, Data integrity in regulated bioanalysis: a summary from the European bioanalysis forum workshop in collaboration with the MHRA, *Bioanalysis* 11 (13) (2019) 1227–1231, <http://dx.doi.org/10.4155/bio-2019-0139>.
- [16] Food and Drug Administration, Data Integrity and Compliance With Drug CGMP. Questions and Answers. Guidance for Industry, 2018 (accessed 17.10.19) <https://www.fda.gov/media/119267/download>.
- [17] European Medicines Agency, Guidance on Good Manufacturing Practice and Good Distribution Practice: Questions and Answers, Data Integrity, 2016 (accessed 17.10.19) [https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory/research-development/compliance/good-manufacturing-practice/guidance-good-manufacturing-practice-good-distribution-practice-questions-answers#data-integrity-\(new-august-2016\)-section](https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory/research-development/compliance/good-manufacturing-practice/guidance-good-manufacturing-practice-good-distribution-practice-questions-answers#data-integrity-(new-august-2016)-section).
- [18] Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA), "GXP" Data Integrity Guidance and Definitions, 2018 (accessed 17.10.19) <https://assets>.

- publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/687246/MHRA_GxP_data_integrity_guide_March_edited_Final.pdf.
- [19] R.P. Webster, C.F. Cohen, F.O. Saeed, H.N. Wetzel, W.J. Ball Jr., T.L. Kirley, A.B. Norman, Evaluation of methods to reduce background using the python-based elisa-qc program, *J. Immunol. Methods* (2018), <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jim.2018.02.013>.
- [20] H.N. Wetzel, C. Cohen, A.B. Norman, R.P. Webster, A novel Python program for implementation of quality control in ELISA, *J. Immunol. Methods* (2017), <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jim.2017.05.012>.
- [21] G. van Rossum, Python tutorial, Tech. Rep. CS-R9526, centrum voor Wiskunde en Informatica (CWI), Amsterdam (May 1995); S. Bassi, a primer on Python for life science researchers, *PLOS Comput. Biol.* 3 (11) (2007) 1–6, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.0030199>.
- [22] O. Travis E, A Guide to Numpy, accessed: 2019-04-30 (2006). S. Stéfan van der Walt, C. Colbert, G. Varoquaux, The Numpy Array: A Structure for Efficient Numerical Computation, 2011, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/MCSE.2011.37> (accessed 30.04.19) <https://www.numpy.org/>.
- [23] E. Jones, T. Oliphant, P. Peterson, et al., SciPy: Open Source Scientific Tools for Python, 2001 (accessed 30.04.19) <http://www.scipy.org/>.
- [24] J.D. Hunter, Matplotlib: A 2d Graphics Environment, 2007, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/MCSE.2007.55> <https://matplotlib.org/>.
- [25] W. McKinney, Data structures for statistical computing in python, in: S. van der Walt, J. Millman (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 9th Python in Science Conference*, 2010, pp. 51–56 <https://pandas.pydata.org>.
- [26] D. Farrell, 2016. DataExplore: an application for general data analysis in research and education, *J. Open Res. Softw.* 4 (1) (2019) e9, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5334/jors.94> (accessed 30.04.19).
- [27] R. Storn, K. Price, Differential evolution – a simple and efficient heuristic for global optimization over continuous spaces, *J. Glob. Optim.* (1997) 341–359.
- [28] G. Banach, M. Bawiec, B. Kołodziej, G. Garbacz, J. Paszkowska, M. Wiater, ELISA Tool, 2020 (accessed 07.04.20) <https://gitlab.com/physiolutionpl/elisa-tool>.
- [29] M. Azadeh, B. Gorovits, J. Kamerud, S. MacMannis, A. Safavi, J. Sailstad, P. Sondag, Calibration curves in quantitative ligand binding assays: recommendations and best practices for preparation, design, and editing of calibration curves, *AAPS J.* 20 (1) (2017) 22, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1208/s12248-017-0159-4>.
- [30] W.N. Cumberland, Y. Fong, X. Yu, O. Defawe, N. Frahm, S.D. Rosa, Nonlinear calibration model choice between the four and five-parameter logistic models, *J. Biopharm. Stat.* 25 (5) (2015) 972–983, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10543406.2014.920345>.
- [31] D.W. Hosmer, J.S. Lemeshow, R.X. Sturdivant, *Applied Logistic Regression*, Third Ed., Wiley, 2013, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/9781118548387>.
- [32] *Guidance for Industry. Computerized Systems Used in Clinical Investigations*, 2007 (accessed 17.12.19) <https://www.fda.gov/media/70970/download>.
- [33] A.K. Rattan, Data integrity: history, issues, and remediation of issues, *PDA J. Pharm. Sci. Technol.* 72 (2) (2018) 105–116, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5731/pdajpst.2017.007765>.
- [34] G.R. Grant, E. Manduchi, A. Pizarro, C.J. Stoeckert Jr., Maintaining data integrity in microarray data management, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 84 (7) (2003) 795–800, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/bit.10847>.
- [35] V. Steinwandter, C. Herwig, Provable data integrity in the pharmaceutical industry based on version control systems and the blockchain, *PDA J. Pharm. Sci. Technol.* 73 (4) (2019) 373–390, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5731/pdajpst.2018.009407>.
- [36] F. Darrouzain, S. Bian, C. Desvignes, C. Bris, H. Watier, G. Paintaud, D. de Vries, Immunoassays for measuring serum concentrations of monoclonal antibodies and anti-biopharmaceutical antibodies in patients, *Ther. Drug. Monit.* 39 (4) (2017) 316–321, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/FTD.0000000000000419>.